

D2.1 Mapping RIRs and priorities for joint strategy

Report

Version 0.8

WP2 Team

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Version History		
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0.1	31/12/2021	First strategic benchmarking internal version
0.2	03/02/2022	First draft conclusions presented to the Una Europa Research Strategy Group
0.3	04/02/2022	First CH mapping report internal version
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0.7	22/03/2022	Final version for WP internal review
0.8	28/03/2022	Final version submitted to the project coordination team

Executive summary

Deliverable 2.1 “Mapping RIRs and priorities for joint strategy” reports on the results of the mapping exercise carried out in order to analyse assets, needs, barriers and enablers for sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources (RIRs) across Una Europa universities, as defined by Task 2.2 “Mapping of research infrastructures and resources”.

RIRs play a fundamental role in the advancement of knowledge and technology and their exploitation. They also contribute to regional, national, European and global development and can be considered as one of the most important facilitators of international cooperation in science. The European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures states that “research infrastructures are also crucial in helping Europe lead a global movement towards open, interconnected, data-driven and computer-intensive research, experimental development. They increase the creativity in and efficiency of research and bridge the gap between highly developed and lesser-developed regions.” The European Union emphasized the role of RIRs through many policies, programmes and documents.

In this document, we use some of them as main references, including reports on the following topics: the European Research Area (ERA) (EC DG R&I 2021), the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) (ESFRI 2020), the European Charter of access for research infrastructures (EC DG R&I, 2016; OECD/Science Europe, 2020), the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC SB 2021), the EU’s open science policy. These references constitute the backbone of the analysis of our WP2 mapping exercise.

The objective of WP2 is to develop a strategy and an action plan for sharing research infrastructures and resources across Una Europa universities and to start exploring concrete paths and formats for sharing infrastructures through initial steps to co-design pilot studies. Within Una.Resin, sharing infrastructures is a key pillar to moving towards a barrier-free common R&I ecosystem.

WP2 focuses on 2 global challenges: 1. Promoting the wellbeing of human and animals in a sustainable and healthy environment, to address existing, emerging/re-emerging and novel global One Health threats (One Health); 2. Promoting cultural heritage to strengthen European values and cohesion (Cultural Heritage). The focus on these global challenges also has important connections and synergies with the other focus areas of Una Europa: European studies, Sustainability, and Data Sciences and Artificial Intelligence.

The benchmarking has been fulfilled by the implementation of three mapping exercises: 1 - Benchmarking Una Europa member universities’ R&I strategies; 2 – Mapping of the RIRs related to the challenge “Exploring cultural heritage to strengthen inclusion and participative communities”; 3 – Mapping of the RIRs related to the challenge “Promoting the wellbeing of human and animals in a sustainable and healthy environment”. The first questionnaire has been implemented in cooperation with WP1 and included 2 sections. Section 1 concerned the R&I policies and strategic initiatives (connected to WP1 task 1.2). Section 2 concerned the RIR strategies, policies and initiatives. It addresses the following key aspects: assets; policies, practices and management systems; access regimes; support services and specific requirements for sharing RI and other resources; RIRs that

underpin Open Science, including legal framework, institutional strategies; links with ESFRIs & EOSC.

The two thematic mapping processes have been co-designed with all relevant stakeholders (in particular the Self-Steering Committees and Research Infrastructure Cluster). For executing these mappings, common mapping tools, i.e., a Concept Note for the delineation of the thematic scope of the mapping exercise and a questionnaire aimed at describing in details the mapped RIRs, were designed.

The strategic benchmarking questionnaire as well as the Concept Notes and the questionnaires of the thematic mappings on Cultural Heritage and One Health (Annexes 1, 2a, 2b, 3a and 3b) represent a useful toolkit that can be adapted, improved and re-used for future mapping exercises, for example, for other focus areas of Una Europa. The entire list of the mapped infrastructures, along with their URL and three keywords to describe their field of work, is also attached in this report.

Section 1 "Benchmarking Una Europa member universities' RIRs strategies, policies, initiatives": main findings

Section 1 reports the comparative analysis aimed at understanding and benchmarking the existing strategies, policies and initiatives of the eight Una Europa universities in order to identify complementarities, strengths, opportunities and barriers for opening up and sharing RIRs.

Our analysis of overall frameworks, strategies, policies, gaps and needs (i.e., financial, human, legal and others) for sharing RIRs suggests that the most added value to foster collaborations within and beyond Una Europa is **to focus our joint strategy and action plan on interconnecting RIRs, including small- and medium-size ones**, rather than condense all our efforts on large-scale EU-related RIRs.

Pooling this vast constellation of large-scale, small and medium-sized RIRs by encouraging joint cooperation is necessary for several reasons.

Firstly, providing support to small and medium sized RIRs, as they are usually deeply rooted and well-integrated in their local substrate, is most likely to gather and engage a wide community of stakeholders, across all disciplinary fields. This position truly aligns with one of the Una Europa's project objective in involving citizens and non-academic actors across all regions of our Una Europa ecosystem.

Secondly, this will also allow the multiple interconnections that already exist between ESFRI initiatives or national roadmap Research Infrastructures and smaller scale RIRs (see sections 2 and 3) to be reinforced and expanded. This is likely to increase and facilitate knowledge transfer from RIRs with good experience to those with less. Strengthening the RIRs ecosystem at that level will

certainly open new routes of collaboration and, thereby, enhance our competitiveness at larger, European and international scales.

Thirdly, small and medium-sized RIRs are suffering from a severe lack of funding, since most of the funds available to Una Europa institutions are being targeted towards larger scale infrastructures (cf. Chapter 2). Una Europa support has a pivotal role in this regard: by creating a common space for knowledge, tools and practices exchanges and by offering ramp-up funding (if feasible), opening and sharing of RIRs can be significantly accelerated.

Encouraging cross-institutional links between these different categories (small-medium-large) of RIRs would therefore be highly beneficial for our academic community. To achieve this, the adoption of joint visions (and willingness) for opening and sharing RIRs across our universities is needed.

We thus propose to include in the overall Una Europa strategy a "Una RIRs without Borders" Labelling Initiative. The main aim of this initiative would be to agree on common guiding principles, on which we could rely to build our ecosystem of RIRs for Research, Innovation and Education within Una Europa. This would rely on four key actions:

1. To lay the groundwork for a joint strategy and action plan for RIRs, we suggest co-designing a **Charter for Research Infrastructures** that would encourage the adoption of common - and very general – principles.
2. To Allocate **seed funding** for initial research collaborations or short mobilities for the opening and sharing of RIRs, as a first stimulus and to test the feasibility of cross-institutional access to RIRs.
3. To manage RIRs according to similar principles is a prerequisite to ease their opening and sharing at the Una Europa level and beyond. In this regard, focusing on improving the specific skills of personnel involved in the management of RIRs is fundamental. Yet, our analysis shows that the diversity of profiles involved in the development of RIRs makes it difficult to have a unique proposition on skills upgrading and upscaling. Therefore, the most added value for Una Europa would be to **strengthen skills and knowledge related to RIRs management through a mutual learning process** building on the existing initiatives and structures (e.g. Una Europa Clusters expertise, staff mobility schemes, etc.) and drawing on the richness and complementary strengths of Una Europa Universities. Mobility of staff between Una universities in a multidisciplinary and transnational perspective would be central in this mutual learning process. Actions directed towards this mutual learning process could start from the **ongoing mobility initiatives** (e.g., "Live my life" joint format for job shadowing) and would develop **new formats, such as webinars on RIRs-related topics** (such as developing and interconnecting RIR tools including database, software, research archives etc.), and targeted seminars/workshop open to all stakeholders. Open Science will play an important role in this process. **Building on the existing framework of RitrainPlus project¹**, which is specifically devoted to the management skills of RIRs staff and involves all Una Europa Universities (as either beneficiaries or as associated partners), will be an asset. Our proposal is to create in Una.Resin, a meaningful and systematic connection between Una.Resin and the RitrainPlus project, for example, by creating synergies at the communication and dissemination level.

¹ <https://ritrainplus.eu/>

4. In parallel, the ambition is also to **advocate** at national and EU levels, together with other alliances (and also through national working groups, LERU, Guild, EUA, FOREU...) **for funding calls and synergies of funds more oriented towards the specific ecosystems of RIRs** and promote Universities RIRs as strategic valuable assets.

This is, however, not without **challenges**:

- Our analysis illustrates the *competitive nature, limited number and fragmented character* of RIRs funding schemes. This severely affects the successful and sustainable development of RIRs beyond their establishment phase, and raises doubts about a possible synergy of funds that would effectively combine regional, national and European financial sources. Una Europa, in providing a space for sharing best experiences and initial, small-scale, financial support, can help to overcome this hurdle.
- Our analysis also sheds light on *the different levels and structures of RIRs management models*, which can considerably vary across institutions and scientific fields. There is no single model to suit but some key factors or guiding principles can be identified. This is one of the main aims of the “Una RIRs without Borders” initiative, and more particularly of the abovementioned Charter.
- Similarly, digital or physical tools, methods and resources that underpin RIRs, are extremely varied and field specific. Important *technical, logistic, legal and financial constraints* may hamper their opening and sharing from an interdisciplinary and transnational perspective. As aforementioned, underneath is the necessary condition to truly promote the willingness for opening and sharing RIRs. This can be further explored through small pilot projects supported by seed funding and mutual learning activities.

Section 2 - Mapping of the RIRs related to the challenge “Exploring cultural heritage to strengthen inclusion and participative communities”: main findings

From the analysis of the questionnaires collected within this mapping exercise, which is focused on the field of Cultural Heritage, some meaningful complementarities emerged in the added value that the mapped RIRs represent for the Una Europa universities. In particular, the results reveal the richness of the assets, both in terms of quantity and quality.

The map contains high level infrastructures, unique infrastructures and resources, world-renowned collections and laboratories containing multilingual and multicultural sources with broad geographical and chronological coverage. The non-exhaustive list includes: infrastructures responding to interdisciplinary challenges; high-end technologies; interdisciplinary networks; wide range of

information and photographic documentation; Open Access publication platforms; unique combination of documentary, scientific and artistic collections; unique interdisciplinary experience; portal for machine and human access; visual analysis tools. Apart from the specific features, the real added value is to explore the possibility to connect, share and open up the RIRs listed within this report.

The report considered two different types of barriers: **barriers to the opening of the RIRs to internal and external users** and **barriers that could hamper collaboration with other universities of Una Europa**. Moreover, we can consider also the field on missing RIRs which could significantly contribute to the analysis, since they represent not only barriers but also an initial “map” of needs that could be the basis for matching across Una universities.

The major obstacles that could hamper collaboration with other universities are the following: limited access and sharing capacities due to **financial constraints**; **access restrictions** due to registration constraints, bureaucracy, mobility and **restrictions due to legal rules** (mainly Intellectual Property (IP) rules) or regulatory (ethical compliance) constraints such as copyright; third parties IP rights inconsistent application of fairness principles; privacy and safety rules. However, a large number of infrastructures declared no barriers. Other barriers are represented by **language**, access limitations due to a **lack of staff** and **limited capacities** due to physical (e.g., lack of space), technical and technological constraints. Altogether, the obstacles emerged seem to confirm the **need to improve the culture of sharing**, by creating a community of practices and a framework of practices for sharing RIRs. Future initiatives should focus on this issue to build a transversal approach aimed at a cultural change that could enable the sharing of RIRs.

This commonality in the barriers faced by the RIRs could lead to consider possible **common solutions**. In the next steps of the implementation of the project Una.Resin, this could be considered as a main topic to work upon. It would be difficult to consider a common answer to these specific barriers, due to the different management models of the RIRs, as well as the different legal frameworks and funding systems. A preliminary step for overcoming these barriers could be to work across Una universities to co-design common principles and guidelines for opening and sharing RIRs.

Section 3 - Mapping of the RIRs related to the challenge “Promoting the wellbeing of human and animals in a sustainable and healthy environment”: main findings

This mapping exercise, which is focused on the field of One Health, emphasizes some complementarities in the added value that the RIRs represent for the Una Europa universities. As it

was mentioned for the Cultural Heritage mapping exercise, the results based on the analysis of the questionnaires reveal the richness of the assets, both in terms of quantity and quality.

The general considerations are coherent with the previous mapping. Regarding the quantity, given the self-selection, this mapping exercise does not give a full picture of what is available in the universities of Una Europa. However, the results obtained provide preliminary insights on the great potential of sharing RIRs in the One Health field, giving a first idea of many possibilities for future developments. It has to be considered that this mapping result is a work in progress that could be updated in order to improve the completeness of the mapping and further explore sharing possibilities among the universities.

Regarding the quality, the map contains high level, unique infrastructures, world-renowned collections and laboratories. A not exhaustive list includes: equipment for biochemical, optical, structural analyses, sequencing and screening systems, tissue and culture facilities, a number of animal facilities, high power computing facilities, geophysical or oceanographic survey devices, dating techniques or prototyping services. These assets belong to a wide range of scientific fields from medtechs and biotech, medical sciences, public health and safety, animal health, to ecology and climate sciences, psychology, ethics and philosophy, bioeconomy, geography, geochemistry and geophysics, archaeology, astronomy. As it was highlighted by the research, important **databases** are also characterising the OH RIRs landscape, offering significant assets to be shared within Una Europa. In fact, one of the main challenges addressed by the One Health approach could be to connect databases (human, animal, environmental) for monitoring and time series in a coordinated manner that normally do not communicate with each other to produce new ones. Another equally important point is to directly engage with users of these facilities. We gathered RIRs information as a 'provider' for extensive services to offer, whereas 'users' (particularly so in One Health) will offer additional views on what and how to open and share RIRs.

Again, it is worth to stress that, beyond the specific features of each infrastructure, the real added value of the RIRs listed within this analysis is to explore paths for opening and sharing them between the Una universities.

The report considered two different types of barriers: **barriers to the opening of the RIRs to internal and external users** and **barriers that could hamper collaboration with other universities of Una Europa**. Moreover, we can consider also the field on missing RIRs which could significantly contribute to the analysis, since they represent not only barriers but also an initial "map" of needs that could be the basis for matching across Una universities.

The analysis of the obstacles that could hamper collaboration with other universities of Una Europa revealed that about half of the RIRs mapped declared that there are no obstacles or have not answered the question, thus implicitly admitting that they do not have particular obstacles to signal. Considering the obstacles mentioned *by the other half* of the RIRs a new type of barrier emerges on the top of the abovementioned list: limitations connected to a **lack of qualified staff**. The second barrier is the one connected to **registration constraints, bureaucracy, mobility**. It is particularly important to note in the field of OH that the high clearance of ethical and privacy rights is required in conducting experiments and valorising research results. The third barrier is the limited sharing capacities due to financial constraints and important **lack of funds**.

It is worth to underline that within the "Una Europa R&I workshop" organized within WP1 in September 2021, sharing of data and data infrastructures has been a topic of the discussion in terms of both

“enablers” and “obstacles” from the infrastructures, ecosystems and multidisciplinary research points of view. An urgent need for enhancing processes of storing, sharing and accessing data emerged and it should be taken into consideration for future steps.

These results are coherent with what has emerged from the analysis of the strategic benchmarking (Section 1). As it was previously said for the Cultural Heritage thematic mapping, the obstacles that emerged in the analysis give the perception of the necessity to work on a community of practices and a framework of practices for sharing RIRs, that was also emphasized in chapter 6 of section 1. Future initiatives should focus on this item to build common solutions and a transversal approach but taking account theme-specific barriers aimed at a cultural change that could enable the sharing of RIRs.